

On the Study of Acid-insoluble Iodates with Radioactive Tracers

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Homogeneous and heterogeneous distribution laws have been studied with RaE and UX₁ as guests and iodates of bismuth, zirconium, cerium (IV) and lead as hosts. Bismuth iodate takes up UX₁ through mixed crystal formation both at tracer and finite concentrations of the guest component.

In the case of zirconium iodate as host and UX₁ as guest, zirconium iodate has been found to take up UX₁ through mixed crystal formation. Zirconium iodate does not take up RaE through mixed crystal formation. Lead iodate takes up neither UX₁ nor RaE through mixed crystal formation. In the case of UX₁, the extent of uptake is very low. Of the host components, which take up UX₁ through mixed crystal formation, partition values in the case of bismuth iodate as host is highest. Bismuth can easily be removed as sulphide, leaving carrier-free UX₁ in solution. A method for the quantitative recovery of carrier-free UX₁ or tetravalent actinides has been developed by the use of bismuth iodate as carrier, which does not take up trivalent actinide analogues like Eu^{152,154} and many of the fission products like Sr^{89,90} and Y⁹⁰. As regards the preparation of a carrier-free tetravalent actinide source, free from trivalent actinides, bismuth iodate is recommended as a dependable carrier in day-to-day laboratory work. Mechanism of the uptake and the compositions of these iodates have been discussed briefly.

Tetravalent ions are well known to form iodates which are insoluble in acids. This property has been mostly utilised in the separation of zirconium, thorium, and cerium (IV) from trivalent rare earths. Zirconium iodate has all along been used as a carrier for UX₁, tracer cerium (IV), and tetravalent actinides in day-to-day procedure. Its crystal structure or even its composition has not yet been perfectly known. Nature of the uptake of such a useful carrier is still unknown.

Bismuth and lead are known also to form iodates, insoluble in mineral acids. Ionic radii of bivalent lead and trivalent bismuth are also near to those of cerium (IV) and thorium. Value of the ionic radius of zirconium is not also very far off and it is also tetravalent. A distribution study with the iodates of zirconium, bismuth, lead, and cerium (IV) as hosts and UX₁ and RaE as guests may provide some clue to the nature of the uptake in question. Bismuth shows some similarity with tetravalent actinides as regards its nature of uptake. In correlating the study on the uptake of bismuth in this series of investigations, an attempt has been made to utilise bismuth iodate for the separation of UX₁ from U₁.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carrier-free UX_1 from natural uranium and RaE from RaD were prepared by the method already developed². Bismuth nitrate, zirconium nitrate, ceric sulphate, potassium iodate, and other reagents used in this investigation were all of AnalaR variety. RaD in equilibrium with RaE was supplied by Mosars. Phillips Duphar.

Preparation of Carrier-free UX_1

Carrier-free UX_1 was prepared by bismuth iodate method. To uranyl nitrate, taken in a beaker, bismuth nitrate solution was added. Precipitation was carried out by adding potassium iodate or iodic acid (0.35*M*) in 4*N*- HNO_3 medium under constant stirring. The precipitate was centrifuged, washed with 0.35*M* potassium iodate or iodic acid solution in 4*N*- HNO_3 medium till free of uranium, and then it was transferred to a beaker. Dilute nitric acid was added to it and the iodate was decomposed by adding oxalic acid (2 g.); iodine liberated was removed by boiling. Excess of oxalic acid was decomposed by HNO_3 . The solution was diluted to maintain acidity between 0.5*N* and 1*N*. Bismuth was precipitated as bismuth sulphide which was removed by filtration. Carrier-free UX_1 remained in the filtrate.

Study of Distribution Coefficients

To the host component in a mineral acid solution (1*N*), taken in a beaker, the activity was added. Variations in the precipitation procedure were made by adding different amounts of potassium iodate solution from a burette. The system was under constant stirring during precipitation. The solution was then centrifuged and a fraction of the solution was pipetted out having a filter paper cap at the delivery end of the pipette. Activity and the host component remaining in solution were determined. The homogeneous distribution coefficients (*D*) and the heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) were calculated as described in an earlier communication.¹

TABLE I

Heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) in acid-insoluble iodate system.

Period of shaking = 5 min.

% Host component separated.	% Guest component carried.	λ value.	<i>D</i> value.	Comments.
1. Bismuth iodate. UX_1 .				
(a) 36.8	39.8	1.10	1.14	With carrier-free UX_1 activity at room temp. ($\sim 32^\circ$)
50.1	54.4	1.13	1.19	
60.0	65.1	1.15	1.24	
75.3	76.5	1.04	1.07	
		Av. 1.11		
(b) 35.7	41.5	1.21	1.28	In presence of $0.916 \times 10^{-4}M$ thorium at room temp. ($\sim 32^\circ$)
49.1	54.4	1.16	1.24	
58.0	64.4	1.19	1.31	
67.0	75.0	1.25	1.48	
		Av. 1.20		

2. Parakayastha and Rao, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 555.

TABLE I (contd.)

% Host component separated.	% Guest component carried.	λ value.	D value.	Comments.
2. Cerio iodate.				
	RaE.			
(a) 41.9	44.6	1.08	1.12	With carrier-free RaE activity at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
63.0	65.5	1.04	1.07	
83.4	82.9	0.98	0.97	
		Av. 1.03		
	RaE.			
(b) 40.3	35.7	0.86	0.82	In presence of $1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$ bismuth at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
48.2	43.9	0.88	0.84	
63.0	61.3	0.95	0.93	
83.7	79.7	0.88	0.70	
		Av. 0.89		
	UX ₁ .			
(c) 47.7	25.8	0.46	0.38	With carrier-free UX ₁ activity at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
64.8	40.0	0.49	0.36	
76.4	49.0	0.49	0.31	
83.0	55.0	0.45	0.25	
		Av. 0.47		
3. Zirconium iodate.				
	RaE.			
(a) 14.8	18.3	1.26	1.29	With carrier-free RaE at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
28.2	34.0	1.25	1.31	
59.3	61.5	1.15	1.24	
79.7	79.7	1.00	1.00	
	RaE.			
(b) 29.6	27.4	0.91	0.90	In presence of $1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$ bismuth at room temp. ($\approx 28^\circ$)
57.1	57.0	1.00	1.00	
80.2	91.5	1.52	2.66	
	UX ₁ .			
(c) 32.4	28.0	0.84	0.81	With carrier-free UX ₁ at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
46.2	42.3	0.89	0.85	
80.0	56.0	0.89	0.85	
		Av. 0.87		
4. Lead iodate.				
	UX ₁ .			
(a) 36.8	57.0	1.80	2.30	With carrier-free UX ₁ at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
45.9	62.0	1.60	1.90	
55.0	65.0	1.30	1.60	
64.5	71.6	1.20	1.40	
	RaE.			
(b) 17.7	70.0	6.20	10.80	With carrier-free RaE at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
27.0	81.0	5.30	11.50	
36.6	88.0	4.60	12.70	
	RaE.			
(c) 15.9	15.7	0.99	0.98	In presence of $1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$ bismuth at room temp. ($\approx 32^\circ$)
26.0	39.0	1.64	1.82	
31.2	59.7	2.43	3.27	
36.8	81.4	3.73	7.68	

Initial conc. of the host components: (1) bismuth = $0.027 M$; (2) cerium (IV) = $0.0218 M$; (3) zirconium = $2.19 \times 10^{-2} M$; (4) lead = $8.4 \times 10^{-2} M$.

TABLE II

Time required for attainment of equilibrium in internally formed acid-insoluble iodate systems at 35°.

Time	% Host component separated.	% UX_1 carried.	<i>D.</i>	% Host component separated.
1. Bismuth iodate.				
24 hr.	69.5	77.6	1.52	44.3
48	69.5	76.5	1.43	57.0
75	69.5	75.7	1.37	63.8
96	69.5	77.2	1.48	70.4

TABLE III

*Homogeneous distribution factor (*D*) in acid-insoluble iodate system at 35°. Period of shaking = 4 days.*

Time	% Host component separated.	% UX_1 carried.	<i>D.</i>	% Host component separated.	% UX_1 carried.	<i>D.</i>	λ .
1. Bismuth iodate.					1. Bismuth iodate.		
24 hr.	69.5	77.6	1.52	44.3	40.7	1.24	1.17
48	69.5	76.5	1.43	57.0	64.9	1.30	1.24
75	69.5	75.7	1.37	63.8	71.4	1.42	1.23
96	69.5	77.2	1.48	70.4	77.6	1.45	1.23
							Av. 1.22
2. Zirconium iodate					2. Zirconium iodate.		
24	53.5	42.3	0.64	44.5	35.0	0.67	0.73
48	53.9	41.0	0.59	58.0	48.0	0.67	0.75
72	53.9	38.6	0.54	66.6	58.7	0.71	0.81
96	54.0	38.7	0.54	75.9	68.0	0.67	0.80
							Av. 0.68
3. Lead iodate.					3. Lead iodate		
24	55.7	47.0	0.70	37.1	24.3	0.54	
48	55.7	39.5	0.52	46.4	22.4	0.33	
72	55.7	37.0	0.47	55.7	41.6	0.57	
96	55.7	41.6	0.57	65.0	38.6	0.34	

Initial concentration of the host components (Tables II and III): (1) bismuth = $0.027 M$; (2) zirconium = $2.19 \times 10^{-2} M$; (3) lead = $3.4 \times 10^{-2} M$.

TABLE IV

**Role of bismuth iodate on the study of preparing carrier-free tetravalent actinides.*

Bitaken per 80 ml.	KIO_3 or HIO_3 (20 ml) in $4M-HNO_3$ added.	% Activity carried.	Final recovery of carrier-free UX_1 .	Comments.
1 (a) 0.226g.	0.35 <i>M</i> - KIO_3 soln.	UX_1 . (k) 99.4 (l) 99.0 (m) 99.0 (n) 100.0		Uranyl nitrate used as a source of UX_1 = 400 mg./80 ml. In case of (k), (l), and (m), activity was measured from the filtrate after washing. In case of (n), bismuth iodate carrying UX_1 was dissolved in dil. HCl and activity was measured.
1 (b) 0.226g.	0.35 <i>M</i> - HIO_3 soln.		(k) 87.3 (l) 91.0 (m) 89.5	Uranyl nitrate used as a source of UX_1 = 80 mg./80 ml. A single coprecipitation with bismuth iodate was enough to get the daughter free from the mother. Absence of uranium was examined by ferrocyanide test in the carrier-free product.

TABLE IV (contd.)

Bi taken per 60 ml.	KIO ₃ or HIO ₃ (20 ml) in 4M-HNO ₃ added.	% Activity carried.	Final recovery of carrier-free %UX ₄ .	Comments.
1 (e) 0.220g.	0.35M-HIO ₃ soln.		(k) 98.0 (l) 85.0 (m) 91.7 (n) 88.0	In case of (k) and (l) we started with 400 mg. uranyl nitrate in 60 ml and last trace of uranium was removed from the daughter by dissolving bismuth iodate and reprecipitating it back. In case of (m) and (n) the procedure was tested by carrier-free UX ₄ , using double precipitation as was done in the previous cases.
2 (a) 0.226 g.	0.35M-KIO ₃ soln.	Eu ^{150,154} . (k) 1.8 (l) 1.3 (m) 1.6		Activity was measured from the filtrate in case of (k) and (l). In case of (m) activity was measured by dissolving bismuth iodate in dilute hydrochloric acid after proper washing.
2 (b) 0.226 g.	Do	Sr ^{90,90} mixed with Y ⁹⁰ . 4.20 2.00		Activity was measured from the filtrate after separation.
2 (c). 0.226 g.	Do	Sr ^{89,90} free from Y ⁹⁰ . 0.44 0.48	..	Activity was measured by dissolving bismuth iodate in dilute hydrochloric acid after proper washing.
2 (d). 0.226 g.	Do	Zr ⁹⁵ and Nb ⁹⁵ . 93.50 94.00		Activity was measured from the filtrate after washing.

* UX₄ was taken as the representative of the tetravalent actinides.

DISCUSSION

Data on the uptake of different iodates as hosts and guests have been included in Tables I and III for convenience. Bismuth iodate has been found to take up UX₄ through mixed crystal formation. The heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) has been found to be constant both at finite and tracer concentrations of UX₄ (Table I). In verifying the homogeneous distribution factor, the internally formed host component was equilibrated for four days in the conventional way, keeping the extent of precipitation the same, when no change in the extent of uptake with respect to period of equilibration (Table II) was found. Constancy of D was therefore examined in the internally formed system after shaking for four days. Table III shows that D assumes an increasing trend with the increasing amount of the host component (bismuth iodate) in the solid phase, whereas λ remains

8; Seaborg and Katz, "The Actinide Elements", National Nuclear Energy Series, IV-14A, McGraw Hill, p 86.

4. McLeese and Peterson, paper 19.8 of "The Transuranium Elements", National Nuclear Energy Series, Division IV, volume 14B, McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, 1949.

constant under identical conditions with UX_1 . Constancy of λ values even after prolonged equilibration indicates the extent of diffusion and recrystallisation in the system to be negligibly small. Tables I and III show that λ values, computed from quick precipitation and those from prolonged equilibration, are near about the same. This particular fact is an evidence that freshly formed bismuth iodate does not differ in morphology with the aged samples. Thus bismuth iodate takes up UX_1 through mixed crystal formation. We studied the coseparation of RaE (bismuth) as guest and ceric iodate as host to support our findings. Such a host was chosen for avoiding radioactivity due to thorium and also to study the phenomenon by reversing the host and the guest. As most of the ceric compounds are morphologically analogous to thorium, such a choice practically served our purpose. Table I (2a and 2b) shows that the uptake of bismuth by ceric iodate takes place through mixed crystal formation both at tracer and finite concentrations of bismuth. That cerium(IV) is a representative of thorium in this system under consideration was verified by the study of the uptake of UX_1 by ceric iodate. Table I (2c) shows that the uptake, as expected, takes place through mixed crystal formation.

Table I(3a and 3b) shows that zirconium iodate takes up RaE both at finite and tracer concentrations through adsorption. A different picture is, however, found in the case of UX_1 as guest. Both the homogeneous and heterogeneous distribution factors are found constant (Tables I and III).

It was of interest to examine the composition of the host components like iodates of zirconium and bismuth in presence of excess of the cations in question under the same experimental condition in which the constancy of D and λ were examined. In case of bismuth it was found that the composition may be represented as $Bi(IO_3)_3 \cdot XH_2O$. But in case of zirconium iodate, analytical data showed that the composition of the host component was like $2 ZrO(IO_3)_2 \cdot HIO_3 \cdot XH_2O$. This particular ratio (2:5) was the same when the solid phase was freshly precipitated or when the phase in question was equilibrated for a long time. A double salt of thorium iodate has also been mentioned in the literature³. Probably unstable double iodate of thorium takes the role of the uptake through mixed crystal formation. Lack of uptake through mixed crystal formation in the case of bismuth as guest and zirconium as host is probably due to the fact that bismuth does not form double iodate of similar morphology. Incidentally, the composition of the solid phase was determined by examination of the components remaining in solution after addition of a known amount of potassium iodate.

Results in Table I (4a and 4b) show that neither UX_1 nor RaE are taken up by lead iodate through mixed crystal formation. Uptake in both the cases shows an adsorption picture. The partition values in Table I show that bismuth iodate is expected to be a better carrier of UX_1 than zirconium iodate though zirconium iodate⁴ has been used extensively in radiochemical operation for removing tetravalent ions from solution. Table IV records the efficiency of bismuth iodate as a carrier of UX_1 and final preparation of carrier-free source. Table IV(1a) shows that near about cent per cent UX_1 is carried by bismuth iodate. Washing of the precipitate with a solution of iodate and nitric acid does not remove any activity. In the case of uranium (up to 50 mg. as uranyl nitrate in 80 ml), no appreciable amount of uranium is carried by bismuth iodate, but with higher concentration of uranium, some amount of uranium is carried. In case of about 400 mg. of uranyl nitrate

in 60 ml, a double precipitation is essential to obtain UX_1 free of the mother; no appreciable loss in the process has been observed. The solution containing recovered UX_1 on evaporation provided the maximum solid matter to the extent of 1 to 5 mg. Final yield was also about 85 to 98% (Table IV). In bismuth iodate method, bivalent ions like strontium and trivalent ions of the rare earth group are not carried. Uraanyl ion also does not interfere in obtaining tetravalent actinides like carrier-free UX_1 . Zirconium and niobium, however, have been found to interfere. For the preparation of carrier-free UX_1 , this method is better than that by a separation through zirconium iodate or bismuth phosphate. Bismuth iodate therefore can be recommended in the case of separating tetravalent actinides instead of using bismuth phosphate or zirconium iodate.

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